

Unveiling Catalyst-Induced Branching in Polybutadiene Rubber: An In-Depth Investigation

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Abstract: The set of variability tests on polybutadiene rubber (BR) revealed differences in properties between the catalytic systems. These differences are revealed by the conventional criteria for BR characterization (Mooney viscosity and Branching). The Mooney Viscosity (MV) depends on the structure of the raw material and chain Branching. Today, these criteria are used to predict the behaviour of BR during processing. BR has been produced by different Ziegler – Natta catalytic processes. Generally, different catalysed BR has high Branching, moderate Branching, and low Branching. So, we have added more focus on long chain Branching (LCB) and molecular weight distribution (MWD) of the polymer to get more processing benefits. To get those properties Premier RPA has been used. Additionally, chemical properties are also tested for BR samples to get more insight into polymer behaviour.

Index terms: Polybutadiene rubber, Branching, Long chain Branching (LCB), Catalyst

I. INTRODUCTION

Polybutadiene rubber (BR) is a homopolymer of 1, 3 butadiene. This rubber is manufactured by both emulsion and solution processes. However, the solution process is used predominantly for BR production. In the solution process, BR is produced by anionic and Ziegler Natta catalyst type. In that case wide range of cis BR can be produced. Nowadays different manufacturing technologies developed by different suppliers. Polybutadiene rubber is generally characterized by the microstructure (cis content) and macrostructure (molecular weight distribution and degree of Branching). The developer of the polymer has an aim to produce 100% cis content [1]. Due to excellent mechanical properties, BR is the most popular synthetic rubber when combined with polymers like natural rubber (NR) and styrene butadiene rubber (SBR). BR is also used widely because of its low glass transition temperature (T_g). This low value indicates low vinyl content in the molecule. In the vinyl units, the double bonds are pendent to the main chain, and it tends to cross-linking under high-temperature. However, polymers with high vinyl contents are less thermally stable than low vinyl polymers [2].

Polybutadiene rubber of uranium catalyst was identified to achieve the highest level of cis 1, 4 linkages but it is not pursued due to hazardous characteristics [3]. BR with neodymium catalyst (Nd BR) and nickel catalyst (Ni BR) gives linear microstructure whereas cobalt catalysed BR (Co BR) has a wide molecular weight distribution (MWD). This kind of BR has a high level of Branching [4]. The alkyl lithium catalyst or anionic catalyst system produces a polymer with 40-50% cis, 10% vinyl, and the rest of the trans content. This kind of BR is probably the most versatile because, growing chain-ends contain a negative charge (anion), which can further react with coupling agent to make a variety of polymers. Due to growing living anion, this kind of polymer is very linear with narrow molecular weight distribution [5].

In this study, four sets of BRs have been chosen and two types of polymers are present in every set. The four set of BRs are as follows, Co BR, Ni BR, Nd BR, and Li BR. In which first three BRs are high cis BR, and last BR is of low cis BR. Now, in this work it is primarily focused on the polymer long chain Branching (LCB) index, molecular weight (MW), storage modulus (G'), and loss modulus (G'').

II. EXPERIMENTAL

II. 1 MATERIALS

In this study, different types of BR from different suppliers were used for experimentation,

Table 1: Details of the Polybutadiene rubber (BR) along

Sl no	Material	Supplier
1	Co catalyst BR 1	Reliance Industries Limited, Gujarat, India
2	Co catalyst BR 2	Reliance Industries Limited, Gujarat, India
3	Ni catalyst BR 3	Nizhnekamsk, Russia
4	Ni catalyst BR 4	Nizhnekamsk, Russia
5	Nd catalyst BR 5	Nizhnekamsk, Russia
6	Nd catalyst BR 6	Nizhnekamsk, Russia
7	Li catalyst BR 7	Reliance Industries Limited, Gujarat, India
8	Li catalyst BR 8	Reliance Industries Limited, Gujarat, India

II. 2 CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION

II. 2. 1 Ash Content

Ash content of the polymers was studied by following ASTM D 4574. 2 g of preheated sample (125°C/1 hr) was exposed to 550°C for 16 hr in a crucible. It was then taken out, covered, and allowed to be cooled at room temperature. The covered crucible was again heated for 0.5 hr. The above process was repeated till we achieve a constant weight. The constant weight of the crucible was taken which leads to the determination of the ash content.

II. 2. 2 Volatile matter

Volatile matter of polymers studied as per ASTM D 5668. The volatile content was determined by heating a sample of 2 g in an oven at 105°C for 2 hr. The loss in weight is noted as volatile matter (%).

II. 2. 3 Cis BR content

Cis BR content of the polymers was determined as per IS 10016 Standard. For that 0.1 g of the rubber sample was taken and dissolved completely in toluene over a period of 24 hrs time. After that a film of 0.1 mm thickness was casted over the KBR pellet using a metal spacer and the film along with the KBR pellet was used in FTIR scanning for a range of 1200 to 600 cm⁻¹. Based on the absorbance peak at the respective position of cis (724 cm⁻¹ to 793 cm⁻¹), the percentage of cis content was determined using the respective formula.

$$C_0 = 1 \times \text{cis peak}$$

$$C_t = 0.118 \times \text{trans peak}$$

$$C_v = 0.164 \times \text{vinyl peak}$$

$$\text{Cis percent by Mass} = \frac{C_0 \times 100}{C_0 + C_t + C_v}$$

II. 2. 4 Molecular Weight Distribution (MWD)

The ASTM D6474 test protocol was used to assess the molecular weight distribution and molecular weight averages of polybutadiene rubbers. In this ASTM D6474 test technique, desired PBR sample was dissolved in a solvent and injected onto the chromatographic column(s) packed with a solid substrate. This allows the solution's molecules to be separated according to size. The separated molecules are detected and recorded as they elute from the column in the concentration-ordered sequence. Calibration converts receipt timings to molecule weights. The molecular weight distribution and average molecular weight parameters are computed using data on molecular weight concentration.

II. 3 PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION

II. 3. 1 Mooney Viscosity: Mooney viscosity [ML (1 + 4) @ 100°C] of the polymer and Mooney Stress relaxation behaviour of the polymer was studied by using a Mooney viscometer (Premier model, Alpha Technologies, Akron, USA, by following the test method ASTM D1646.

II. 3. 2 Temperature sweep study: The sweep study of virgin polymer was measured by using a Premier Rubber process analyser (PRPA, Alpha Technologies, Akron, USA) operating at a frequency of 100 cpm and 7% strain.

II. 3. 3 Large Amplitude Oscillatory Shear (LAOS) study: The LAOS study was performed by using a Premier Rubber Process Analyzer (PRPA, Alpha Technologies, Akron USA) at a temperature of 150 °C, frequency of 0.1Hz and strain of 1000%.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III. 1 CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION

In the case of chemical properties, the volatile matter, and ash content for all BR samples is similar (**Table 2**), whereas cis content is low for Li BR as compared to other polymers. The difference what is observed in molecular weight distribution values is because of the branching and linearity of the polymer.

Table 2: Chemical characteristics of different types of Polybutadiene rubber

Test Parameter	Test Method	BR1	BR2	BR3	BR4	BR5	BR6	BR7	BR8
Volatile matter, %	ASTM	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02
	D5668								
Ash Content, %	ASTM	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01
	D5667								
Cis BR Content, %	IS-10016	96.5	96.5	97.0	97.0	96.9	97.0	53.0	54.0
	(part-4)								
GPC Study:	By GPC	412784	459659	462540	508499	480313	465104	251990	253784
Mw									
Mn									
(PDI) Mw/Mn									
		88628	94050	96619	118568	186028	201182	92094	90995
		4.66	4.89	4.79	4.29	2.58	2.31	2.74	2.79

III. 2 PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Raw rubber exhibits a unique viscoelastic nature, possessing characteristics that are neither purely viscous nor elastic. Consequently, the term 'characterization' takes on varied meanings for different individuals. In the context of gum rubber, fundamental characterization properties often revolve around parameters such as Mooney viscosity. Also, this parameter is very crucial for rubber processing for all the rubber manufacturers and end users. From the assessment of viscosity (Figure 1), BR 1 and BR 2 exhibit higher values, while BR 8 shows lower viscosity. This discrepancy in viscosity levels serves as an indicator of the presence of Long Chain Branching (LCB) within the polymers. The observed variations highlight the influence of LCB on the rheological properties of the materials

Figure 1: Viscosity of different type of Polybutadiene rubbers

Dynamic testing is often used to assess rheological and processability behaviour of polymers. "Key parameters derived from dynamic testing play a pivotal role for characterizing polymer behaviour, particularly the storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G''), and tan delta. The storage modulus is a measure of stored energy or elasticity. The loss modulus indicates lost energy or viscous property. The tan delta is derived from storage modulus and loss modulus (G''/G'). A Higher tan delta indicates the polymer is prone to flow under stress conditions, while a lower tan delta indicates the resistance to flow [6]. Our focus in this study is directed towards comprehending the dynamic characteristics through an examination of G' , G'' , and tan delta for the polymer (Table 3 & 4).

Table 3: Application Example of Temperature sweep (G' vs Temperature)

Temp/ G' (kPa)	BR 1	BR 2	BR 3	BR 4	BR 5	BR 6	BR 7	BR 8
35°C	133.33	132.32	167.86	170.23	176.35	189.50	184.90	185.78
55°C	115.55	116.80	144.35	146.29	150.42	170.92	170.80	172.64
75°C	103.16	104.74	124.52	127.48	130.40	140.41	138.81	137.73
95°C	95.49	96.38	109.27	115.16	110.87	114.85	109.96	109.08
115°C	90.30	90.03	99.52	103.20	102.29	96.45	103.96	99.66
135°C	83.90	83.54	92.11	95.34	94.73	81.15	78.56	80.41

Table 4: Application Example of Temperature sweep (G'' vs Temperature)

Temp/ G'' (kPa)	BR 1	BR 2	BR 3	BR 4	BR 5	BR 6	BR 7	BR 8
35°C	80.50	80.03	116.15	118.78	120.12	143.35	142.79	143.88
55°C	77.44	77.49	112.89	115.67	119.44	132.89	128.03	128.66
75°C	73.45	73.86	104.41	106.32	111.40	122.84	115.73	112.38
95°C	70.94	71.31	93.77	95.74	104.06	111.94	110.62	109.69
115°C	69.33	69.28	89.44	91.09	98.86	101.61	99.06	97.69
135°C	66.44	66.02	85.20	86.29	94.45	90.75	87.17	86.56

The higher values of storage modulus (G') across the temperature range signify increased stiffness within the polymer chain. Such polymers are likely to impart higher stiffness at the compound level when blended with fillers and other

ingredients under controlled conditions. This observation underscores the potential for tailoring the mechanical properties of polymer compounds through strategic formulation and processing. From **Table 3**, it is observed that BR 5 to BR 8 (Nd BR and Li BR) is less branched and exhibits a good extent of stiffness [7-8]. On the contrary, both BR 3 and BR 4 exhibit moderate G' values consistently across the temperature range, indicating the possible presence of branching in the polymer chain. BR 1 and BR 2 display low G' values from 35°C to 135°C, revealing the occurrence of branching in the polymer chain. These observed phenomena serve as indicators of the structural characteristics influencing the mechanical behaviour of the polymers.

Analysis of **Table 4** reveals a low G'' value for BR 1 and BR 2, both of which involve the use of a Cobalt catalyst. This observation points to specific rheological properties associated with the Cobalt-catalysed polymers, suggesting distinctive behaviour in terms of energy dissipation and viscoelastic characteristics. That low value also indicates the low entanglement of chain for this polymer. At the same time, it is high for Nd and Li catalyst polymers (BR 5 to BR 8). Once again, it is evident that Nickel-catalysed polybutadiene rubber (Ni BR) likely exhibits fewer branches compared to its Cobalt-catalysed counterpart (Co BR). The data presented in the above tables substantiates the conclusion that Co BR is indeed branched, while Nd and Li BR demonstrate less branched characteristics. Moreover, Ni BR displays a pattern of reduced branching compared to Co BR, yet still maintains a level of branching higher than that observed in Nd and Li BR [9].

.Analysis of Figure 1 provides further insights into the relationship between Mooney viscosity and polymer branching. It becomes evident that there is a direct dependency between the two, wherein increased branching corresponds to higher polymer viscosity. This observation underscores the influential role of branching in shaping the rheological properties of the polymer, particularly its viscosity profile.

Table 5: Application Example of Temperature sweep (tan delta vs Temperature)

Temp/tan delta	BR 1	BR 2	BR 3	BR 4	BR 5	BR 6	BR 7	BR 8
35°C	0.604	0.605	0.692	0.698	0.681	0.756	0.772	0.774
55°C	0.670	0.663	0.782	0.791	0.794	0.777	0.75	0.745
75°C	0.712	0.705	0.838	0.834	0.854	0.875	0.834	0.816
95°C	0.743	0.740	0.858	0.831	0.939	0.975	1.006	1.006
115°C	0.768	0.770	0.899	0.883	0.966	1.053	0.953	0.980
135°C	0.792	0.790	0.925	0.905	0.997	1.118	1.110	1.076

Figure 2: tan delta difference of different catalyst Polybutadiene rubbers

Upon examining the data presented in **Table 5** & **Figure 2**, a notable observation is the substantial difference in tan delta between high temperature (135°C) and low temperature (35°C) for BR 5 to BR 8. This disparity implies that these polymers exhibit resistance to flow, attributed to their linearity and narrow molecular weight distribution. In contrast, BR 1 and BR 2 demonstrate a lower tan delta difference, suggesting a broader molecular weight distribution indicative of branching. Additionally, BR 3 and BR 4 exhibit a moderate balance between branching and linearity when compared to the other polymer.

Figure 3: Lissajous Figures of studied Polybutadiene rubbers

Analysing the Lissajous figures for the examined BR samples, a noticeable trend emerges, revealing a difference in Long Chain Branching (LCB) content. The figures exhibit similarities between BR1 to BR4 (Co and Ni catalysed), showcasing elevated levels of Long long-chain branching (LCB). Conversely, BR5 and BR6 (Nd catalysed) as well as BR7 and BR8 (Li catalysed) demonstrate a distinct similarity, characterized by significantly lower LCB content. BR5 to BR8 exhibit a markedly reduced level of LCB, as discerned from the graphical representation. This is manifested by a distinct deviation in the loading segment of the stress from its unloading counterpart. Consequently, as the level of LCB increases, there is a corresponding augmentation in the loop surface, effectively mitigating distortion and maintaining balance within the system.

Table 6: LAOS Test by using Rubber Process Analyzer

Parameter	BR 1	BR 2	BR 3	BR 4	BR 5	BR 6	BR 7	BR 8
$(G')_1$	4.13	4.14	4.17	4.18	2.46	2.45	3.34	3.27
$(G')_3$	-0.88	-0.89	-0.87	-0.89	-0.83	-0.84	-1.22	-1.22
$(G')_5$	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.30	0.30	0.38	0.37
LCB	6.32	6.26	6.34	6.36	3.65	3.56	3.35	3.21

The impact of Long Chain Branching is highly significant in various processes including extrusion, injection molding, compression molding, and blow molding. The presence of branching serves to augment chain entanglements, prolong relaxation times, and elevate the extensional flow viscosity. This is exemplified by the observed phenomenon of strain hardening, emphasizing the pivotal role of branching in influencing the rheological behavior during processing [10]. G'_1 represents the storage modulus at the fundamental frequency, while G'_3 and G'_5 signify contributions from higher harmonic signals. In a linear polymer, the Lissajous shear stress vs. strain rate curve typically displays a distinctive double loop pattern. However, this characteristic double-loop behavior is not observed in polymers containing long-chain branching structures, as illustrated in Figure 3. This phenomenon has been consistently reported in numerous LAOS analyses conducted on rubber elastomers [11-12]. A formulated empirical equation has been devised for the

purpose of calculating the long-chain branching index in rubber elastomers, as detailed in previous studies (Equation 1) [13, 14]

$$LCB = \frac{G'_{15}}{G'_{5}} - \left[\frac{5}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{G'_{30}}{G'_{15}} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G'_{30}}{G'_{5}} \right) \right] \text{----- (1)}$$

Negative LCB index value indicates a predominantly linear polymer structure. Conversely, a higher LCB index signifies an increased presence of branching structures within the polymer, BR5 and BR6 (Nd catalysed), along with BR7 and BR8 (Li catalysed), exhibit a distinct similarity marked by significantly lower Long Chain Branching (LCB) content. BR5 to BR8 showcase a notable reduction in LCB levels, indicating a less branched structure in comparison.

Table 7: Mooney Stress relaxation Test by using Mooney Viscometer

Parameter	BR 1	BR 2	BR 3	BR 4	BR 5	BR 6	BR 7	BR 8
Tx80 (s)	65.48	65.15	65.8	67.64	24.86	31.81	26.12	26.52

The relationship between stress relaxation and the molecular weight of a polymer is significant. Generally, higher molecular-weight polymers tend to exhibit slower rates of stress relaxation compared to lower molecular weight polymers [15]. This relationship arises from the differences in chain mobility and entanglement between polymers of different molecular weights. This study shows low branched polymers BR5 to BR8 with low molecular weight shows a higher rate of stress relaxation and higher LCB BR 1 to BR4 with High molecular weight showed lower rate of stress relaxation.

Figure 4: Mooney Stress relaxation Vs Time chart for different catalysed BR

Polymers with good stress relaxation properties such as BR 1 to BR 4 can undergo deformation more easily during processing, such as extrusion, molding, or stretching. This results in smoother processing operations with reduced risk of defects or failure.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study delved into the nuanced characteristics of polybutadiene rubber (BR) derived from various catalytic systems, shedding light on the intricate relationship between polymer structure and processing behavior. Through a comprehensive analysis of chemical and physical properties, several key insights were gleaned. The catalytic system employed significantly impacts the microstructure and macrostructure of BR. While cobalt-catalyzed BR exhibited high levels of branching, nickel-catalyzed BR displayed moderate branching, and neodymium and lithium-catalyzed BRs showcased less branching. Chemical characterization revealed similarities in volatile matter and ash content across different BR samples, while significant differences were observed in cis BR content. This variance directly correlated with the branching and linearity of the polymer. Mooney viscosity emerged as a crucial parameter for assessing polymer processing behavior, with higher viscosity indicating increased branching. Dynamic testing

elucidated the rheological properties, highlighting the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') as indicators of stiffness and energy dissipation, respectively. Analysis of temperature sweep data and LAOS tests provided valuable insights into LCB content. BR samples with lower LCB exhibited resistance to flow and enhanced stiffness, while those with higher LCB demonstrated increased flexibility and entanglement. The study revealed a correlation between molecular weight, branching, and stress relaxation behavior. Polymers with higher molecular weight and lower branching exhibited slower rates of stress relaxation, facilitating smoother processing operations. In essence, the comprehensive characterization of BR polymers elucidated the intricate interplay between catalyst type, polymer structure, and processing behavior. By understanding these relationships, manufacturers can optimize formulation and processing parameters to tailor BR properties according to specific application requirements, thereby enhancing product performance and quality.

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